

Sl. No.

015870

KERALA STATE OPEN SCHOOL

HIGHER SECONDARY OPEN REGULAR / PRIVATE REGISTRATION

STD XI ANNUAL PUBLIC - EXAMINATION 2006 - 2007

MARK / GRADE CARD

Name of candidate

Joby John

Name of Exam. Centre

Govt. Hss Pala Code 05-006

Reg. Number

14354

Subjects	Marks awarded				Grade Obtained
	CE	PE	TE	Total	
Maximum Marks →	20	20	60/80	100	
Part I English	19	-	42	61	B
Part II Second Language (Syrac)	20	-	77	97	A ⁺
Part III Optional Subjects 1 History	20	-	34	54	C ⁺
2 Sociology	17	-	36	53	C ⁺
3 Political Science	18	-	35	53	C ⁺
4 Economics	17	-	34	51	C ⁺

Promoted/not promoted to class XII

Date of Issue

28/4/07

Signature of Principal
Name and Designation

PRINCIPAL

Govt. H. S. S.,
Pala.

Minimum Marks required

TE : 30%

PE : 40%

Total for each subject : 30 %

Marks	90-100	80-89	70-79	60-69	50-59	40-49	30-39	20-29	Below 20
Grade	A ⁺	A	B ⁺	B	C ⁺	C	D ⁺	D	E

GOVERNMENT OF KERALA
BOARD OF HIGHER SECONDARY EXAMINATION
HIGHER SECONDARY EXAMINATION (CLASS XII)

No. HSE 199254

CERTIFICATE

Register Number **4116301**

This is to certify that Mr. **JOBY JOHN** appeared for the
HIGHER SECONDARY EXAMINATION (HUMANITIES GROUP) held in **MARCH 2008**
 He/She is **ELIGIBLE** for higher studies.

The Scores and Grades obtained by the Candidate are shown below :

SUBJECTS	SCORES								Grade Obtained	Grade in Words
	CE		PE		TE		TOTAL			
	Score Obtained	Max. Score								
PART I ENGLISH	19	20			54	80	73	100	B+	B plus
PART II SYRIAC	20	20			79	80	99	100	A+	A plus
PART III (Optionals) HISTORY	19	20			53	80	72	100	B+	B plus
ECONOMICS	17	20			52	80	69	100	B	B only
POLITICAL SCIENCE	19	20			60	80	79	100	B+	B plus
SOCIOLOGY	18	20			64	80	82	100	A	A only

Eligibility for Higher Studies: B+ or above for all subjects

[Handwritten Signature]

Place: _____
 Date: **15.05.2008**

SECRETARY
 Board of Higher Secondary Examinations,
 Government of Kerala

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No.3431/Leg.C1/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

A 013352

Section: **CBCSS - V**

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam

Student ID: **SAAAAE2009E020000172**

25-Feb -2010

GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate : **JOBY JOHN**
 Name of College : **ST THOMAS COLLEGE PALA**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN) : **SAAA09103202** Degree: **Bachelor of Arts**
 Programme : **English**
 Stream : **Model I - English**
 Name of Examination : **First Semester Examination November 2009**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Grade Point Averages				GPA for the Course	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Grade Awarded	Result
			Theory		Practical						
			ISA	ESA	ISA	ESA					
Common Course I											
EN01AA901	English - Communication Skills in English	4	3.80	2.68	-	3.75	3.16	3.07	2.44	B	Pass
EN01AA902	English - Reading Literature in English	3	3.40	3.24	-	-	3.28	2.98	1.75	B	Pass
Common Course II											
SY01AB901	Syriac - Poetry, Grammar and History of Syriac Language and Literature	4	3.80	3.84	-	-	3.83	2.84	2.44	A	Pass
Core Course											
EN01BA901	Methodology Of Humanities And Literature	4	3.80	3.68	-	-	3.71	3.62	2.03	A	Pass
Complementary Course I											
PS01CA901	Politics - An Introduction to Political Science	4	3.40	3.64	-	-	3.58	2.82	1.91	A	Pass
	FINAL RESULT	19	-	-	-	-	3.52	-	-	A	Pass

(ISA - In-Semester Assessment, ESA - End Semester Assessment, IA pertains to GPA for ISA only. UA pertains to GPA for ESA only.)

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No.3431/Leg.C1/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

A 089443

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam

04-Aug-2010

Section: CBCSS - V

Student ID: SAAAAE2009E020000172

GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate : **JOBY JOHN**
 Name of College : **ST. THOMAS COLLEGE, PALAI**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN) : **SAAA09103202** Degree: **Bachelor of Arts**
 Programme : **English**
 Stream : **Model I - English**
 Name of Examination : **Second Semester April 2010**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Grade Point Averages				GPA for the Course	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Grade Awarded	Result
			Theory		Practical						
			ISA	ESA	ISA	ESA					
Common Course I											
EN02AA901	English - Critical Thinking, Academic Writing & Presentation	4	3.80	3.12	-	-	3.29	2.93	1.89	B	Pass
EN02AA902	English - Musings on Vital Issues	3	3.40	3.04	-	-	3.13	2.76	1.66	B	Pass
Common Course II											
SY02AB901	Syriac - Poetry, Grammar and History of Syriac Literature	4	3.80	3.96	-	-	3.92	3.33	3.15	A	Pass
Core Course											
EN02BA901	Introduction To The Study Of Language And Literature	4	3.60	3.28	-	-	3.36	3.45	1.85	B	Pass
Complementary Course I											
PS02CA902	Politics - Governmental machinery & Processes	4	3.80	2.88	-	-	3.11	3.46	2.52	B	Pass
	SEMESTER RESULT	19	-	-	-	-	3.37	-	-	B	Pass

(ISA - In-Semester Assessment, ESA - End Semester Assessment, IA pertains to GPA for ISA only. UA pertains to GPA for ESA only.)

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No.3431/Leg. Cl/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

C 140514

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam

12-Sep-2012

Section: CBCSS - V

Student ID: SAAAAE2009E020000172

GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate : **JOBY JOHN**
 Name of College : **ST. THOMAS COLLEGE, PALAI**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN) : **SAAA09103202** Degree: **Bachelor of Arts**
 Programme : **English**
 Stream : **Model I - English**
 Name of Examination : **Third Semester Examination November 2010**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Grade Point Averages				GPA for the Course	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Grade Awarded	Result
			Theory		Practical						
			ISA	ESA	ISA	ESA					
Common Course I											
EN03AA901	English - Reflections on Indian Polity, Secularism & Sustainable Environment	4	3.60	3.96	-	-	3.87	2.23	1.86	A	Pass
Common Course II											
SY03AB901	Syriac - Prose, Grammar and History of Syrian Church in India	4	3.80	4.00	-	-	3.95	3.22	3.05	A	Pass
Core Course											
EN03BA901	Literature And Informatics	4	3.60	3.92	-	-	3.84	1.61	2.42	A	Pass
EN03BA902	Reading Prose	4	3.60	4.00	-	-	3.90	2.85	2.38	A	Pass
Complementary Course II											
EN03CA901	English - Evolution of Literary Movements: The Shapers of Destiny	4	3.80	3.32	-	-	3.44	1.63	2.06	B	Pass
	SEMESTER RESULT	20	-	-	-	-	3.80	-	-	A	Pass

(ISA - In-Semester Assessment, ESA - End Semester Assessment, IA pertains to GPA for ISA only. UA pertains to GPA for ESA only.)

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No.3431/Leg. CI/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

C 140519

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam

12-Sep-2012

Section: CBCSS - V

Student ID: SAAAAE2009E020000172

GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate : **JOBY JOHN**
 Name of College : **ST. THOMAS COLLEGE, PALAI**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN) : **SAAA09103202** Degree: **Bachelor of Arts**
 Programme : **English**
 Stream : **Model I - English**
 Name of Examination : **Fourth Semester Examination April 2011**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Grade Point Averages				GPA for the Course	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Grade Awarded	Result
			Theory		Practical						
			ISA	ESA	ISA	ESA					
Common Course I											
EN04AA901	English - Evolution of the philosophy of Science : Literary Perspectives	4	3.80	3.68	-	-	3.71	2.60	1.97	A	Pass
Common Course II											
SY04AB901	Syriac - Prose, Grammar and History of Syrian Church in India	4	3.80	A	-	-		3.08	3.11	-	Fail
Core Course											
EN04BA901	Reading Poetry	4	3.80	A	-	-		3.47	2.19	-	Fail
EN04BA902	Reading Fiction	4	3.80	A	-	-		3.37	2.21	-	Fail
Complementary Course II											
EN04CA901	English - Evolution of Literary Movements: The Cross-currents of Change	4	1.80	A	-	-		3.38	1.93	-	Fail
	SEMESTER RESULT	20	-	-	-	-		-	-	-	Fail

(ISA - In-Semester Assessment, ESA - End Semester Assessment, IA pertains to GPA for ISA only. UA pertains to GPA for ESA only.)

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No.3431/Leg. CI/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

C 140510

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam
12-Sep-2012

Section: CBCSS - XIII

Student ID: SAAAAE2009E020000172

GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate : **JOBY JOHN**
 Name of College : **ST. THOMAS COLLEGE, PALAI**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN) : **SAAA09103202** Degree: **Bachelor of Arts**
 Programme : **English**
 Stream : **Model I - English**
 Name of Examination : **Fourth Semester Examination April 2012 (Reappearance)**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Grade Point Averages				GPA for the Course	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Grade Awarded	Result
			Theory		Practical						
			ISA	ESA	ISA	ESA					
Common Course II											
SY04AB901	Syriac - Prose, Grammar and History of Syrian Church in India	4	3.80	4.00	-	-	3.95	3.24	3.21	A	Pass
Core Course											
EN04BA901	Reading Poetry	4	3.80	3.20	-	-	3.35	2.59	2.10	B	Pass
EN04BA902	Reading Fiction	4	3.80	3.52	-	-	3.59	2.65	2.26	A	Pass
Complementary Course II											
EN04CA901	English - Evolution of Literary Movements: The Cross-currents of Change	4	1.80	3.28	-	-	2.91	2.62	1.93	B	Pass

(ISA - In-Semester Assessment, ESA - End Semester Assessment, IA pertains to GPA for ISA only. UA pertains to GPA for ESA only.)

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No.3431/Leg. Cl/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

C 101696

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam
08-Feb-2012

Section: CBCSS - XIII

Student ID: SAAAAE2009E020000172

GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate : **JOBY JOHN**
 Name of College : **ST. THOMAS COLLEGE, PALAI**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN) : **SAAA09103202** Degree: **Bachelor of Arts**
 Programme : **English**
 Stream : **Model I - English**
 Name of Examination : **Fifth Semester Examination October 2011**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Grade Point Averages				GPA for the Course	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Grade Awarded	Result
			Theory		Practical						
			ISA	ESA	ISA	ESA					
Core Course											
EN05BA901	Reading Drama	4	3.40	3.40	-	-	3.40	3.05	2.48	B	Pass
EN05BA902	Language And Linguistics	4	3.40	3.84	-	-	3.73	3.05	2.15	A	Pass
EN05BA903	Literary Criticism: Theory And Practice	4	3.40	2.76	-	-	2.92	3.12	2.26	B	Pass
EN05BA904	Postcolonial Literatures	4	3.40	2.04	-	-	2.38	3.10	2.29	C	Pass
Open Course											
PH05DAP02	Energy and Environmental Studies	4	3.40	3.00	-	-	3.10	3.00	2.36	B	Pass
	SEMESTER RESULT	20	-	-	-	-	3.11	-	-	B	Pass

(ISA - In-Semester Assessment, ESA - End Semester Assessment, IA pertains to GPA for ISA only. UA pertains to GPA for ESA only.)

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No. 3431/Leg. C/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

IPG45/2012-13

C 140407

Section: CBCSS - XIII
Student ID: SAAAAE2009E020000172

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam

13-Sept-2012

GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate : **JOBY JOHN**
Name of College : **ST. THOMAS COLLEGE, PALAI**
Permanent Register Number (PRN) : **SAAA09103202** Degree: **Bachelor of Arts**
Programme : **English**
Stream : **Model I - English**
Name of Examination : **Sixth Semester Examination April 2012**

Course Code	Course Title	Month and Year of Passing	Credits (C)	Grade Point Averages				GPA for the Course	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Grade Awarded	Result
				Theory		Practical						
				IS	ES	IS	ES					
Programme Result												
EN06BA901	Women's Literature	Apr.2012	4	3.60	3.64			3.63	2.86	2.47	A	Pass
EN06BA902	Indian Writing in English	Apr.2012	4	3.60	2.92			3.09	3.01	2.51	B	Pass
EN06BA903	Comparative Literature	Apr.2012	4	3.00	3.52			3.39	2.67	2.36	B	Pass
EN06BA904	American Literature	Apr.2012	4	4.00	3.60			3.70	3.27	2.40	A	Pass
EN06BF901	Project	Apr.2012	2			4.00	3.80	3.85	3.21	3.05	A	Pass
EN06BB902	Regional Literatures in translation	Apr.2012	4	3.60	2.52			2.79	2.91	2.50	B	Pass
	SEMESTER VI SGPA	Apr.2012	22					3.37			B	Pass
	SEMESTER V SGPA	Oct.2011	20					3.11			B	Pass
	SEMESTER IV SGPA	Apr.2012	20					3.50			A	Pass
	SEMESTER III SGPA	Nov.2010	20					3.80			A	Pass
	SEMESTER II SGPA	Apr.2010	19					3.37			B	Pass
	SEMESTER I SGPA	Nov.2009	19					3.52			A	Pass
	CGPA		120					3.44			B+	Pass
Programme Part Result												
Result Common	Course I -		22					3.43				
Result Common	Course II - Second Lang: Syriac		16					3.91				
Core Group												
Result Core Course -			62					3.40				
Result Complementary Course I - Political Science			8					3.35				
Result Complementary Course II - English			8					3.18				
Result Open Course - Energy and Environmental Studies			4					3.10				
Result Core Group -			82					3.36				

(ISA - In-Semester Assessment, ESA - End Semester Assessment, IA pertains to GPA for ISA only. UA pertains to GPA for ESA only.)

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Register No : SAAA09103202

Month & Year : April 2012

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No. 3431/Leg.C1/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

FACULTY OF LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE

The Syndicate of the Mahatma Gandhi University hereby makes known that Sri **JOBY JOHN** has been admitted to the **Degree of Bachelor of Arts** he having been certified by duly appointed examiners to be qualified to receive the same and having been by them placed in the **B+** grade with a Cumulative Grade Point Average of **3.44** at the examination under Choice Based Course-Credit-Semester System and Grading held in **April 2012** with the following courses.

Common Course I	ENGLISH
Common Course II	SYRIAC
Core Course	ENGLISH
Complementary Course I	POLITICAL SCIENCE
Complementary Course II	ENGLISH
Open Course	ENERGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL STUDIES

Given under the seal of the University.

University Buildings
Priyadarshini Hills P.O.
Kottayam - 686 560
Kerala, India
Dated: 22 JUNE 2013

Vice-Chancellor

Mahatma Gandhi University

2 PG 191 / 2012-13

Sl.No. 151281

SAAAAE2009E020000172

ESTABLISHED BY KERALA STATE
LEGISLATURE BY NOTIFICATION No
3431/Leg CV/85/Law dated 17/04/1985

Kottayam
13-Sept-2012

PROVISIONAL CERTIFICATE

Certified that Sri/Smt **JOBY JOHN**

has passed the following examination of the University with the details as shown below:

Name of the Examination : **BA Degree**

FACULTY OF LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE

Register Number : SAAA09103202
Year of Admission : 2009
Stream : Model I - English
Total Credits : 120
Programme CGPA : 3.44
Grade : B+
Month and Year -
of Passing : April 2012

CONVERSION TABLE:

- Total Credits into Maximum Marks : $(\text{Total Credits} \times 100) / 4$
- CGPA into Marks : $(\text{Total Credits} \times \text{CGPA} \times 25) / 4$
- GPA or SGPA or CGPA into Percentage: $(\text{GPA or SGPA or CGPA}) \times 25$

Section CBCSS - XIII

Checked by

Section Officer

ASSISTANT REGISTRAR
XIV (Exam)

for CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Phone: RPM. 04822-260069 (Vicar)
260323, 263444, 262656 (Office)

ST. AUGUSTINE'S FORANE CHURCH

RAMAPURAM BAZAR P.O. - 686 576, KERALA

Date.....

CERTIFICATE OF BAPTISM

Name	:	Thomas
Baptismal Name	:	Thomas
Family Name	:	Keelath
Baptismal Name of Father	:	John
Baptismal Name of Mother	:	Mary
Native Parish	:	Ramapuram
Date of Birth	:	01/07/1989
Date of Baptism	:	24/07/1989
Place of Baptism	:	Ramapuram
Godfather's Name	:	George Karippakudiyil
Godfather's Parish	:	Ramapuram
Godmother's Name	:	Mariakutty Karippakudiyil
Godmother's Parish	:	Ramapuram
Minister of Baptism	:	Fr. Joseph Vadakkekoottu
Register Reference No.	:	Vol.12;P.132;No.72/89

Certified that the above is a true extract from the baptism register maintained in this church.

Ramapuram
10/05/2016

Rev. Dr. George Njarakunnel
(Fr. Vicar)

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No. 3431/Leg.C1/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

FACULTY OF EDUCATION

The Syndicate of the Mahatma Gandhi University

hereby makes known that

Joby John

has been admitted to the

Degree of Bachelor of Education

he having been certified by duly appointed examiners to be qualified to receive the same and having been by them placed in the A Grade with English Education as Core Course and Health and Physical Education as Complementary Elective Course at the examination held in January 2016.

Register Number : SEAA14255301

Given under the seal of the University

University Buildings
Priyadarshini Hills P.O.
Kottayam - 686 560
Kerala, India

Dated : 18-March-2017

Vice-Chancellor

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No.3431/leg. CI/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

M 086613

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam

Section: EI V

21-Dec-2015

Student ID: SEAAAC2014E02500095

MARK CUM GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate: **Joby John**
 Name of College: **ST THOMAS COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION, PALA**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN): **SEAA14255301**
 Programme: **Bachelor of Education (B.Ed)**
 Stream: **English Education**
 Name of Examination: **First Semester Examination July 2015**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Marks						Grade Awarded (G)	Grade Point (GP)	Credit Point (CP)	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Result
			External		Internal		Total							
			Awarded (E)	Max	Awarded (I)	Max	Awarded (E+I)	Max						
Common Courses														
BE01BA901	Philosophical and Sociological Bases of Education	4	64	80	17	20	81	100	A	9	36	17.03	57.72	Pass
BE01BA902	Psychological Bases of Education	4	46	80	18	20	64	100	C	7	28	17.08	58.45	Pass
BE01BA903	Modern Educational practices	4	52	80	16	20	68	100	C	7	28	17.00	54.59	Pass
Core Courses														
BE01BA904	Theoretical Bases of English Education	4	54	80	17	20	71	100	B	8	32	16.79	61.37	Pass
BE01BA915	Approaches and Practices in Teaching English	4	73	80	16	20	89	100	A	9	36	16.62	59.76	Pass
Complementary Elective Course														
BE01CA903	Health and Physical Education	4	72	80	19	20	91	100	A+	10	40	18.00	60.45	Pass
SEMESTER I RESULT		24	-	-	-	-	464	600	-	-	200	-	-	Pass
SEMESTER CREDIT POINT AVERAGE (SCPA) - 8.33														
SEMESTER GRADE - A														

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No.3431/Leg. CI/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam
09-Jun-2016

Section: EI V

Student ID: SEAAAC2014E02500095

MARK CUM GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate: **Joby John**
 Name of College: **ST THOMAS COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION, PALA**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN): **SEAA14255301**
 Programme: **Bachelor of Education (B.Ed)**
 Stream: **English Education**
 Name of Examination: **Second Semester Examination January 2016**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Marks						Grade Awarded(G)	Grade Point (GP)	Credit Point (CP)	Credit Point Average(CPA)	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Result
			External		Internal		Total								
			Awarded(E)	Max	Awarded(I)	Max	Awarded(E+I)	Max							
Common Courses															
BE02BA901	Development and Management of Education in India	4	56	80	16	20	72	100	B	8	32	17.73	56.99	P	
BE02BA902	Personality Dynamics in Education	4	55	80	15	20	70	100	B	8	32	16.50	57.76	P	
BE02BA903	Common Practical Work - Basic Skills in Child Study, SUPW, Art Education, Health & Physical Education - Practical	2	37	40	38	40	75	80	A+	10	20	35.63	32.44	P	
Core Courses															
BE02BA904	Pedagogic Analysis of English	4	60	80	19	20	79	100	B	8	32	17.17	54.77	P	
BE02BA915	Preparatory Course in Teaching - Practical	2	48	50	49	50	97	100	A+	10	20	46.62	42.52	P	
BE02BA916	Teaching Competence - Practical	6	48	50	49	50	97	100	A+	10	60	45.05	41.63	P	
BE02BA917	Viva-Voce	2	19	20	-	-	19	20	A+	10	20	-	16.62	P	
	SEMESTER II RESULT	24	-	-	-	-	509	600	A		216	9.00	-	-	P
	SEMESTER I RESULT	24	-	-	-	-	464	600	A		200	8.33	-	-	P
	PROGRAMME RESULT	48	-	-	-	-	973	1200	A		416	8.67	-	-	P
	CUMULATIVE CREDIT POINT AVERAGE (CCPA) - 8.67														
	PROGRAMME GRADE - A														

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification
No.3431/Leg. C1/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

Sl.No. 501825

Kottayam
13-Jun-2016

PROVISIONAL CERTIFICATE

Certified that Sri/Smt Joby John
has passed the following examination of the University with the details as shown below:
Name of the Examination : B.Ed Degree Examination January 2016

FACULTY OF EDUCATION

Register Number : SEAA14255301
Grade : A
Core Course : English Education
Complementary -
Elective Course : Health and Physical Education

Section EI V

Checked by

Section Officer

ASSISTANT REGISTRAR (EXAM-VIII)

for CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Phone: RPM. 04822-260069 (Vicar)
260323, 263444, 262656 (Office)

ST. AUGUSTINE'S FORANE CHURCH

RAMAPURAM BAZAR P.O. - 686 576, KERALA

Date.....

CERTIFICATE OF BAPTISM

Name	:	Thomas
Baptismal Name	:	Thomas
Family Name	:	Keelath
Baptismal Name of Father	:	John
Baptismal Name of Mother	:	Mary
Native Parish	:	Ramapuram
Date of Birth	:	01/07/1989
Date of Baptism	:	24/07/1989
Place of Baptism	:	Ramapuram
Godfather's Name	:	George Karippakudiyil
Godfather's Parish	:	Ramapuram
Godmother's Name	:	Mariakutty Karippakudiyil
Godmother's Parish	:	Ramapuram
Minister of Baptism	:	Fr. Joseph Vadakkekoottu
Register Reference No.	:	Vol.12;P.132;No.72/89

Certified that the above is a true extract from the baptism register maintained in this church.

Ramapuram
10/05/2016

Rev. Dr. George Njarakunnel
(Fr. Vicar)

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No. 3431/Leg.C1/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

FACULTY OF EDUCATION

The Syndicate of the Mahatma Gandhi University

hereby makes known that

Joby John

has been admitted to the

Degree of Bachelor of Education

he having been certified by duly appointed examiners to be qualified to receive the same and having been by them placed in the A Grade with English Education as Core Course and Health and Physical Education as Complementary Elective Course at the examination held in January 2016.

Register Number : SEAA14255301

Given under the seal of the University

University Buildings
Priyadarshini Hills P.O.
Kottayam - 686 560
Kerala, India

Dated : 18-March-2017

Vice-Chancellor

**ST. THOMAS COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION
PALA**

Course and Conduct Certificate

Joby Jobo

.....
*was a student of this college, for the B.Ed. course during the
academic year 2014-2015*

His/ Her character and conduct were ... good

Date *2/2/2016*

[Signature]
PRINCIPAL

Section: EI V

Student ID: SEAAAC2014E02500095

MARK CUM GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate: **Joby John**
 Name of College: **ST THOMAS COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION, PALA**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN): **SEAA14255301**
 Programme: **Bachelor of Education (B.Ed)**
 Stream: **English Education**
 Name of Examination: **First Semester Examination July 2015**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Marks						Grade Awarded (G)	Grade Point (GP)	Credit Point (CP)	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Result
			External		Internal		Total							
			Awarded (E)	Max	Awarded (I)	Max	Awarded (E+I)	Max						
Common Courses														
BE01BA901	Philosophical and Sociological Bases of Education	4	64	80	17	20	81	100	A	9	36	17.03	57.72	Pass
BE01BA902	Psychological Bases of Education	4	46	80	18	20	64	100	C	7	28	17.08	58.45	Pass
BE01BA903	Modern Educational practices	4	52	80	16	20	68	100	C	7	28	17.00	54.59	Pass
Core Courses														
BE01BA904	Theoretical Bases of English Education	4	54	80	17	20	71	100	B	8	32	16.79	61.37	Pass
BE01BA915	Approaches and Practices in Teaching English	4	73	80	16	20	89	100	A	9	36	16.62	59.76	Pass
Complementary Elective Course														
BE01CA903	Health and Physical Education	4	72	80	19	20	91	100	A+	10	40	18.00	60.45	Pass
SEMESTER I RESULT		24	-	-	-	-	464	600	-	-	200	-	-	Pass
SEMESTER CREDIT POINT AVERAGE (SCPA) - 8.33														
SEMESTER GRADE - A														

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification No.3431/Leg. CI/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

Priyadarsini Hills P.O,
Kottayam
09-Jun-2016

Section: EI V

Student ID: SEAAAC2014E02500095

MARK CUM GRADE CARD

Name of Candidate: **Joby John**
 Name of College: **ST THOMAS COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION, PALA**
 Permanent Register Number (PRN): **SEAA14255301**
 Programme: **Bachelor of Education (B.Ed)**
 Stream: **English Education**
 Name of Examination: **Second Semester Examination January 2016**

Course Code	Course Title	Credits (C)	Marks						Grade Awarded (G)	Grade Point (GP)	Credit Point (CP)	Credit Point Average (CPA)	Institution Average (IA)	University Average (UA)	Result
			External		Internal		Total								
			Awarded (E)	Max	Awarded (I)	Max	Awarded (E+I)	Max							
Common Courses															
BE02BA901	Development and Management of Education in India	4	56	80	16	20	72	100	B	8	32	17.73	56.99	P	
BE02BA902	Personality Dynamics in Education	4	55	80	15	20	70	100	B	8	32	16.50	57.76	P	
BE02BA903	Common Practical Work - Basic Skills in Child Study, SUPW, Art Education, Health & Physical Education - Practical	2	37	40	38	40	75	80	A+	10	20	35.63	32.44	P	
Core Courses															
BE02BA904	Pedagogic Analysis of English	4	60	80	19	20	79	100	B	8	32	17.17	54.77	P	
BE02BA915	Preparatory Course in Teaching - Practical	2	48	50	49	50	97	100	A+	10	20	46.62	42.52	P	
BE02BA916	Teaching Competence - Practical	6	48	50	49	50	97	100	A+	10	60	45.05	41.63	P	
BE02BA917	Viva-Voce	2	19	20	-	-	19	20	A+	10	20	-	16.62	P	
	SEMESTER II RESULT	24	-	-	-	-	509	600	A		216	9.00	-	-	P
	SEMESTER I RESULT	24	-	-	-	-	464	600	A		200	8.33	-	-	P
	PROGRAMME RESULT	48	-	-	-	-	973	1200	A		416	8.67	-	-	P
	CUMULATIVE CREDIT POINT AVERAGE (CCPA) - 8.67														
	PROGRAMME GRADE - A														

Checked by:

Section Officer:

CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

Mahatma Gandhi University

(Established by Kerala State Legislature by Notification
No.3431/Leg. C1/85/Law, dated 17th April 1985)

Sl.No. 501825

Kottayam
13-Jun-2016

PROVISIONAL CERTIFICATE

Certified that Sri/Smt Joby John
has passed the following examination of the University with the details as shown below:
Name of the Examination : B.Ed Degree Examination January 2016

FACULTY OF EDUCATION

Register Number : SEAA14255301
Grade : A
Core Course : English Education
Complementary -
Elective Course : Health and Physical Education

Section EI V

Checked by

Section Officer

ASSISTANT REGISTRAR (EXAM-VIII)

for CONTROLLER OF EXAMINATIONS

ST. THOMAS COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION, PALA

TRANSFER CERTIFICATE

No. 1555

Date 2/2/2016

Name of Student

Joby John

Admission Number

3950/2014-2015

Date of birth as entered in
the Admission Register

In figures

1/7/1989

In Words

One - Seven - Nineteen

eighty nine

Date of Admission

12/12/2014 PN

Date and time of relieving

2/2/2016 AN

Class in which he / ~~she~~ studied
at the time of leaving

B.Ed

Subjects studied

English Education

Whether the course has
been completed

Yes

Whether he / ~~she~~ has paid all
fees or money dues

Yes

PRINCIPAL

No. 8042/11

പേര്/Name : ജോബി ജോൺ / JOBY JOHN

ആർ/പെൺ/ Sex : ആൺ / Male

ജനന തീയതി/Date of Birth : 01/07/1989
(ONE / JULY / ONE THOUSAND NINE HUNDRED EIGHTY-NINE)

ജനന സ്ഥലം/Place of Birth : ചെറുപുഷ്പം ട്രസ്റ്റ് ഹോസ്പിറ്റൽ പാല, പാല / Cherupushpam Trust Hospital Pala, Pala

മാതാവിൻ്റെ പേര് / Name of Mother : മേരിക്കുട്ടി/ MARYKUTTY

പിതാവിൻ്റെ പേര്/ Name of father : ജോൺ / JOHN

കുട്ടിയുടെ ജനന സമയത്ത് താപനിലയുടെ രേഖീകരണം : *** ലഭ്യമല്ല

Address of the Parents at the time of birth of the child : *** Not Available

മാതാപിതാക്കളുടെ സ്ഥിരമായ മേഖല/Permanent address of parents : കീലത്ത്, രാമപുരം പി ഓ,

KEELATHU, RAMAPURAM P O ,

ജനന രജിസ്ട്രേഷൻ നമ്പർ/ Registration No : 1569/1989

ജനന രജിസ്ട്രേഷൻ തീയതി/ Date of Registration : 11/07/1989

അഭിപ്രായപ്പെടലുകൾ/Remarks (if any) :

*** The original records do not contain the column relating to Current address
*** അസ്സൽ രേഖകളിൽ നിലവിലുള്ള മേഖലയെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള സാമ്പത്തിക കോളങ്ങൾ ഉൾപ്പെടുത്തില്ല

തീയതി /Date of issue : 31/10/2011

തീയതി അധികാരിയുടെ ഒപ്പ്/
Signature of the issuing authority
തീയതി അധികാരിയുടെ മേഖല/Address of the issuing authority

TONY THOMAS
REGISTRAR OF BIRTHS, DEATHS
AND MARRIAGES, PALA MUNICIPALITY
KOTTAYAM DIST., KERALA, INDIA

Ensure Registration of Every Birth and death

ഓരോ ജനനവും മരണവും ജനനവും മരണവും ഉൾപ്പെടുത്തില്ല

भारतीय गैर न्यायिक

दस
रुपये
रु.10

TEN
RUPEES
Rs.10

INDIA NON JUDICIAL

കേരളം കേരल KERALA

19AA 426339

FORM No.5

Form-5

(See Rule 8)

നമ്പർ 15,497

No

കേരള സർക്കാർ

GOVERNMENT OF KERALA

നഗരകാര്യ വകുപ്പ്

DEPARTMENT OF URBAN AFFAIRS

സ്ഥലതലത്തിൽ നൽകുന്ന തദ്ദേശസ്ഥാപനത്തിന്റെ പേര്

പാല മുനിസിപ്പാലിറ്റി

Name of local body issuing certificate

Pala Municipality

ജനന സർട്ടിഫിക്കറ്റ്

BIRTH CERTIFICATE

(Handwritten signature)

TOMY THOMAS
REGISTRAR OF BIRTHS, DEATHS
AND MARRIAGES, PALA MUNICIPALITY

1999-ലെ ജനന-മരണ രജിസ്ട്രേഷൻ ആക്ടിലെ 17 വകുപ്പും 1999-ലെ കേരള ജനന-മരണ രജിസ്ട്രേഷൻ ചട്ടങ്ങളിലെ 13-ാം ചട്ടവും അനുസരിച്ച് നൽകുന്നത്.
(Issued under Section 17 of the Registration of Births and Deaths Acts, 1969 and Rule 13 of the Kerala Registration of Births and Deaths Rules, 1999)

താഴെ പറയുന്ന വിവരങ്ങൾ കേരള സംസ്ഥാനത്തിലെ കോട്ടയം ജില്ലയിലെ മീനച്ചിൽ താലൂക്കിലെ പാല മുനിസിപ്പാലിറ്റി-ലെ (തദ്ദേശസ്ഥാപനം) അസ്സൽ ജനന രജിസ്റ്ററിൽ നിന്ന് എടുത്ത ലിഖിതവയാണെന്ന് സാക്ഷ്യപ്പെടുത്തുന്നു.

(This is to certify that the following information has been taken from the original record of birth which is the register for (local area/local body) Pala Municipality of Meenachil Taluk of Kottayam District of State Kerala.

17.10.2011

ज्ञानदीप विद्यापीठ

Inana-Deepa Vidyapeeth

Pontifical Athenaeum of Philosophy and Religion, Pune

This is to certify that

Joby John

having followed the prescribed curriculum of studies and fulfilled the other requirements of the Bachelor's Degree course in the Faculty of Philosophy, has passed its examinations in the **High First Class** on the 31st day of March, 2019.

Wherefore, by virtue of the authority vested in us, we hereby confer on him the academic degree of

Bachelor of Philosophy

with all its rights, honours and privileges.

Given at Pune on the 9th day of July of the year 2019.

Dean of Philosophy

President / Principal

Registrar

November 15, 2017

ACCREDITATION CERTIFICATE

Following the "Decree on the Reform of Ecclesiastical Studies of Philosophy" (2011) of Congregation for Catholic Education, Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pontifical Institute of Philosophy and Religion, Pune, India offers a three year programme in Bachelor of Philosophy (Baccalaureate or First Cycle).

However, it is to be observed that **JOBY JOHN** has obtained a Bachelor's Degree from a recognised University, prior to his joining for BPh Programme. Taking this into consideration and with the knowledge and approval of Congregation of Catholic Education (See the letter of 10th February 2015, Prot no 78/2015), and after conducting a qualifying examination, **we, hereby, accredit 48 credits to Supplementary Obligatory (24) and Optional Additional Courses (24) of Bachelor of Philosophy**. In order to qualify for Bachelor's Programme, following "Decree on the Reform of Ecclesiastical Studies of Philosophy," Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth requires 180 credits out of which 120 credits are in Obligatory Basic Courses.

Though the Degree of Bachelor of Philosophy at Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth is a three year programme, consisting of 180 credits, the above student has been able to complete the degree validly in less than three years, taking into consideration the accredited credits. The marks given for the accredited credits are not calculated in the final marklist given to the student.

Results of Qualifying Examination

No	Subject	Marks	Credit
1	Advanced English: Grammar and Literature (Supplementary Obligatory)	85	24
2	Bachelor Degree (Optional Additional)	81	24
Total Credits Accredited			48

Kuruvilla Pandikattu SJ

Dean

Dean, Faculty of Philosophy
Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth
Pune- 411 014.

Jose Thayil SJ

Registrar
Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth
PUNE 411 014

Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth

Pontifical Institute of Philosophy and Religion
P.B. 3002, Nagar Road, Ramwadi, Pune 411014

ज्ञानदीप विद्यापीठ

JNANA-DEEPA VIDYAPEETH

Pontifical Athenaeum of Philosophy and Religion

Pune 411 014

Ref.: 2019/17073/1664

Migration Certificate *Character – Attendance*

This is to certify that **Joby John**, who was born on **01 July 1989** in **Pala - Kerala**, has satisfied all the requirements of Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth as regards the courses of studies, examinations and fees, and has been awarded the degree **Bachelor of Philosophy (BPh.)**.

The same **Joby John**, has shown himself to be of **good** character during the period of his studies at Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, from **June 2017 to March 2019**.

He has been awarded the above-mentioned degree after having attended the prescribed courses of study, i.e., two-years of the **Bachelor of Philosophy (BPh.)** course in this Institution.

We have therefore no objection to him continuing higher studies in other Institutions.

Jose Tharid

Registrar

Pune, 9 July, 2019

ज्ञानदीप विद्यापीठ

JNANA-DEEPA VIDYAPEETH
PONTIFICAL ATHENAEUM OF PHILOSOPHY AND RELIGION

Pune - 411014

FACULTY OF PHILOSOPHY

Reg. No. : 17073

Consolidated Marksheet

Dated : 09/07/2019

NAME : JOBY JOHN
DEGREE : Bachelor of Philosophy (BPh.)
COURSE : 2 Years (2017 - 2019)

SUBJECTS	CR.	MARKS	SUBJECTS	CR.	MARKS
Basic Obligatory Subjects			Philosophy of Knowledge II , Advanced Issues (B)	4	65
Natural Theology: Advanced Issues (B)	2	75	Introduction to Philosophy II (B)	2	91
Philosophy Research Project (B)	8	90	History of Philosophy: Modern & Post Colonial (B)	2	82
Philosophy of Knowledge: Phronesis (B)	2	78	Metaphysics: Introductory Issues (B)	2	95
History of Philosophy I (B)	4	82	Indian Studies: Folk Philosophy (B)	2	90
Political Philosophy: Advanced Issues (B)	4	76	Philosophy of Nature II (B)	4	71
Philosophy of Man: Social Issues (B)	2	70	Introduction to Philosophy I (B)	2	86
Philosophy of God: World Religions (B)	4	85	Book Review I (O)	2	78
Philosophy of Knowledge: Introductory Issues (B)	2	86	Political Philosophy: Gandhi and Ambedkar (O)	2	74
Indian Studies: Tribal Philosophy (B)	2	75	Natural Theology: Mysticism and God Experience (O)	2	92
History of Philosophy: Indian Philosophy (B)	4	75	Textual Reading: III (O)	2	85
Logic : Classical & Symbolic (B)	4	96	Philosophy of Man: Death (O)	2	82
History of Philosophy: Modern Philosophy (B)	4	47	Philosophy of Man: Mind (O)	2	40
Indian Studies: Classical Systems (B)	4	81	History of Philosophy: Differance (O)	2	60
Comprehensive Oral Examination (B)	8	80	Philosophy of Man: ConscIOUSness (O)	2	80
Metaphysics: Advanced Issues (B)	4	87	Supplimentary Obligatory Subjects		
Moral Philosophy: General Ethics (B)	4	62	Faith and Reason (B)	4	45
Comprehensive Written Examination (B)	8	78	Research Methodology (B)	4	93
Ethics of Child Protection (B)	2	86	Latin (O)	4	89
Philosophy of Man: Nature & Freedom (B)	4	67	Optional Additional Subjects		
History of Philosophy: Contemporary Philosophy (B)	4	53	Political Philosophy: Capability Enhancement (O)	2	80
Natural Theology: Introductory Issues (B)	4	78	Hindi (O)	2	88
Political Philosophy: Basic Issues (B)	2	67	Pali (O)	2	96

Grade : High First Class

Weighted Average : 77

Total Credits Completed : 140

Jose Thayil

Registrar & Controller of Examinations

Legend : Basic=(B), Optional=(O), Fail=(F), R1=Second Attempt, R2=Third Attempt, Not Obtained(N)
Credits : Credit=(Cr), A credit is a unit of study equivalent to about 15 periods of class and a corresponding period of personal work(30 hours in all)
Key to Marks : A+ 90-100 (High Distinction), A 80-89(Distinction), B+ 70-79(High First Class), B 60-69(First Class), C+ 50-59(Second Class), C 40-49(Pass Class), D 0-39(Fail)

ST. AUGUSTINE'S FORANE CHURCH

RAMAPURAM BAZAR P.O. - 686 576, KERALA

Date 10-5-2016

Confirmation Certificate

This is to Certify that Thomas, s/o
John and Manam, Keelethu received Confirmations
on 29-11-1998 from Mar Joseph Pullichampal
as per the Register kept here.

[Handwritten Signature]

केन्द्रीय माध्यमिक शिक्षा बोर्ड, दिल्ली
Central Board of Secondary Education, Delhi

केन्द्रीय अध्यापक पात्रता परीक्षा (के.अ.पा.प.)
CENTRAL TEACHER ELIGIBILITY TEST (CTET)

(253)890742601003803700196

- FEBRUARY 2016

पात्रता प्रमाणपत्र
ELIGIBILITY CERTIFICATE

अनुक्रमांक Roll No. 03700196

यह प्रमाणित किया जाता है कि This is to certify that **JOBY JOHN**

वर्ग Category **GEN**

माता का नाम Mother's Name **MARYKUTTY JOHN**

पिता/पति का नाम Father's/Husband's Name **JOHN AUGUSTINE**

केन्द्रीय माध्यमिक शिक्षा बोर्ड, दिल्ली द्वारा आयोजित, केन्द्रीय अध्यापक पात्रता परीक्षा में उपस्थित हुए और उनका प्रदर्शन इस प्रकार रहा :-

appeared at Central Teacher Eligibility Test conducted by the Central Board of Secondary Education, Delhi and performed as under:-

पेपर-I (कक्षा I से V) प्राथमिक स्तर Paper-I (For Classes I to V) Primary Stage			पेपर-II (कक्षा VI से VIII) प्राथमिक स्तर Paper-II (For Classes VI to VIII) Elementary Stage			
विषय Subject	अधिकतम अंक Maximum Marks	प्राप्त अंक Marks Obtained	विषय Subject	अधिकतम अंक Maximum Marks	प्राप्त अंक Marks Obtained	
बाल विकास एवं शिक्षाशास्त्र Child Development & Pedagogy	030	NA	बाल विकास एवं शिक्षाशास्त्र Child Development & Pedagogy	030	21	
गणित Mathematics	030	NA	Social Science	060	31	
पर्यावरण अध्ययन Environmental Studies	030	NA				
भाषा I Language I	030	NA	भाषा I Language I	English	030	17
भाषा II Language II	030	NA	भाषा II Language II	Malayalam	030	23
कुल Total	150	NA	कुल Total	150	092	
परिणाम Result :	NOT APPLICABLE		परिणाम Result :	QUALIFIED		

परीक्षा दिनांक Examination held on : 21-02-2016
परिणाम दिनांक Result declared on : 23-05-2016

दिल्ली Delhi
दिनांक Dated : 23-05-2016

निदेशक (सी.टी.ई.टी.)
Director (CTET)

CENTRAL BOARD OF SECONDARY EDUCATION, DELHI
Central Teacher Eligibility Test (CTET) - FEBRUARY 2016

**MARKS
STATEMENT**

Serial No. **F16037221627** Roll No. **03700196**
Candidate's Name **JOBY JOHN**
Mother's Name **MARYKUTTY JOHN**
Father's/Husband's Name **JOHN AUGUSTINE**

Address of the Candidate

JOBY JOHN
KEELATHU
RAMAPURAM BAZAR
RAMAPURAM
KOTTAYAM
KERALA
PINCODE : 686576

470820

Gender **Male**
Date of Birth **01/07/1989**
Category **GEN**
If Differently Abled **No**

Signature of the Candidate

PAPER-I (FOR CLASSES I-V) PRIMARY STAGE

PAPER-II (FOR CLASSES VI-VIII) ELEMENTARY STAGE

PAPER-I (FOR CLASSES I-V) PRIMARY STAGE			PAPER-II (FOR CLASSES VI-VIII) ELEMENTARY STAGE		
SUBJECT	MAX. MARKS	MARKS OBTAINED	SUBJECT	MAX. MARKS	MARKS OBTAINED
Child Development and Pedagogy	30	NA	Child Development and Pedagogy	30	21
Mathematics	30	NA	Social Science	60	31
Environmental Studies	30	NA			
Language-I	30	NA	Language-I English	30	17
Language-II	30	NA	Language-II Malayalam	30	23
Total Marks	150	NA	Total Marks	150	092

DELHI
DATE : **23-05-2016**

Please refer for instructions on the back side

Director (CTET)

GOVERNMENT OF KERALA

CENTRE FOR CONTINUING EDUCATION KERALA

CERTIFICATE

Certificate No.: 151002604

Registration No.: C1405025DCA0189

Online Verification Code: C160011728

Certified that Mr./Ms. **JOBY JOHN**

has successfully completed the course: **Diploma in Computer Application**

at the sub centre

St. Thomas College Pala, Kottayam

for the period from August, 2014 to February, 2015

The candidate has been awarded the Grade **A** for his / her performance

in the examination conducted on October, 2015

Date of Issue: 22.03.2016

Controller of Examinations

DIRECTOR
Centre for Continuing Education Kerala
Thiruvananthapuram

(Grade : A+ - Marks ≥ 91% A - Marks ≥ 81% and < 91% B+ - Marks ≥ 66% and < 81% B - Marks ≥ 51% and < 66% C - Marks : ≥ 25% and < 50%)
To verify this certificate online visit: <http://www.ccek.org/verfy>

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KERALA

CENTRE FOR CONTINUING EDUCATION KERALA

STATEMENT OF MARKS

Name of Course	Diploma in Computer Application
Name of Student	JOBY JOHN
Registration No.	C1405025DCA0189

Subject	Marks Awarded	Maximum Marks
Informatics [DC 01]	133	150
MS Office and Internet [DC 02]	141	150
Linux and Open Office [DC 03]	110	150
PC Techniques [DC 04]	122	150
Malayalam Computing [DC 05]	131	150
Total Marks	637	750
Percentage of Marks	84.93%	
Final Grade	Grade: A	

Grade:

Marks $\geq$ 91%	A+
Marks $\geq$ 81% and $<$ 91%	A
Marks $\geq$ 66% and $<$ 81%	B+
Marks $\geq$ 51% and $<$ 66%	B
Marks $\geq$ 35% and $<$ 51%	C

Compared by:

Verified by:

Date of Issue: 22.03.2016

Controller of Examinations

DIRECTOR
Centre for Continuing Education Kerala
Thiruvananthapuram

EXPERIENCE CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Joby John** has been working in this institute as a **Language Trainer** from **08/11/2012** to **30/11/2013**. He is eminent, tactful and confident in training the students. During his tenure with the institute he was found to be sincere and hardworking. He is amiable in nature and character is well.

We are thankful for his services and wish him all success for his future endeavor.

Thodupuzha

26/12/2013

Joseph Mathew
Joseph

THE DIRECTOR
Emmanuel International -
Education Career
Development Management
Ramapuram Bazar P.O.
Kottayam District, Pin - 686 576